

Transfer of the flame retardancy and post-fire mechanics from polymer materials to glass-fiber-reinforced plastics

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Motivation and Aim

More knowledge is needed about flame protection more specifically, **the fire resistance and flammability of fiber-reinforced polymeric systems and their fire resistance under mechanical stress**. Furthermore, little is known about the mechanical properties and changes during and after a fire of these types of materials.

This project thus aims to **understand the modes of action in flame retardancy and post-fire mechanics** of phosphorus based flame-retardant polymer materials in fiber-reinforced composites and to compare them with pure epoxy resins.

Unidirectional glass-fiber (UD-GF)
640 g/m²
0/90°

Bidirectional glass-fiber (BD-GF)
580 g/m²
0/90°

Results

Pyrolysis - Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Flammability

Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI)

Sample	DGEBA DER331	DGEBA DER331 + GF	
		UD	BD
1 DGEBA	21.1	33.0	30.9
2 DGEBA + 2%InSI + 8%APP	25.7	47.1	36.3

OI / vol.-% (± 0.2)

UL-94

Sample	DGEBA DER331		DGEBA DER331+GF-UD		DGEBA DER331+GF-BD	
	Classification	Burning rate (mm/min)	Classification	Burning rate (mm/min)	Classification	Burning rate (mm/min)
1 DGEBA	HB40	16 ± 4	HB40	0	HB40	0
2 DGEBA + 2%InSI + 8%APP	V0	-	HB40	0	HB40	0

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

Fire Behavior - Cone Calorimeter

Fire Residue - Macroscopic Appearance

Fire residue of flame retardant formulations A) in the neat resin and with B) unidirectional and C) bidirectional glass fibers. Epoxy resin with 8% APP D) without glass fibers and with E) unidirectional and F) bidirectional glass fibers.

Fire Residue - Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEM Images of fire residue of A) neat resin and with B) unidirectional glass fibers. Epoxy with 8% APP C) without glass fibers and with D) unidirectional glass fibers.

Conclusions

Pyrolysis

- The amount of residue increases when resins are transferred to glass fiber composites.
- When transferred to glass fiber composites, $T_{50\%}$ increases and T_{max} decreases.

Flammability

- When transferred to glass fiber composites, the LOI value increase significantly.
- The addition of flame retardants decreases the burning rate.

Fire Behavior

- The HRR, THR, and PHRR decrease when the resins are transferred to glass fiber composites.
- In addition, the modes of action in gas and condensed phase, decrease significantly.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

- The height of the $\tan \delta$ curve decreases as follows: neat resin >> BD GF composite > UD GF composite indicating lower segmental mobility due to the glass fibers and good interfacial adhesion between the resin and fibers.

Conclusions

- The mobility of the polymer chains is negligibly affected when FRs are added for the neat resin and composites.
- The value of T_g (peak of the $\tan \delta$ curve) is around 160°C and the presence of the glass fibers only causes a slight decrease in this value.
- When the glass fibers are added, there is a change in the modes of action of flame retardancy.
- There is an increase in intumescence and charring when the FRs are added. When glass fibers are added the charring and intumescence diminishes.